

**GENERALIZING ACARCATIONAL ASPECTS OF THE POPULAR
UPRISINGS RAISED IN FERGANA VALLEY IN 1916**

SHAKHZODKHUJA ABDURAZZAKOV

Namangan State University,

4th year student of History

shaxzodxojaabdurazzaqov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139615>

Annotation: This work provides brief information about the popular upheavals raised in the Fergana Valley in 1916 and in which areas of the Fergana Valley, how many people from which area will be mobilized for Labor, which uyezd, ovul, villages of the valley the initial efforts of the uprising were raised, and how many people were and how many were wounded and how many.

Keywords: I.Brzhezitsky, Gultepa, Caucasus, N. Ye. Kolesnikov, Zadorbibi Musamuhammedova, Rizvonbibi Ahmadkhanova, Kuntayev, Chuvama, Kipchoqboy Boymirzayev, V.Dombrovsky, Jamaliddin Uvaysov.

The people's movements of 1916 spread to the five uездs of Fergana region; Andijan, Kokand, Namangan, Skobelev (Fergana) and Osh uезд. According to official documents, uprisings and riots took place at least 107 places in Fergana region, 25 places in Samarkand region, 20 places in Syrdarya region. More than 25 thousand people took part in the Margilan uprising in mid-July 1916[1.76-77]. Most of them were made up of poor peasants, poor and artisans, who had come out to fight inequality and injustice. However, local government authorities, with the help of military troops, achieved the suppression of this uprising. 63 people from the rebels were sent to katorga and exile. Among these were Nurmuhammad Ma'zumov, Tajiboy Miraliyev, Layliboy Qasimbayev, Shermuhammad Habibullayev, Kadirjon Mamasodiqkhojayev, Kamoliddin Khalliyev and others[2.132-133].

According to the data provided by the colonial administration, a bloody confrontation of the population with military units took place in 17 places in the Fergana region. On July 9, people were also agitated in Andijan. A huge crowd of local officials drove from the Old City to the new one - through a large street called Skobelev. The andijonians did not forget about the events of 1898, when the fire of Vengeance was now blazing with baralla. They are the Nebula I in Gultepa square. They meet with brzhezitsky. He stands surrounded by Cossacks and police and, hearing the demands of the crowd, orders the Cossacks to shoot them. As a result, three people were killed and 12 injured.

On July 9, during the suppression of the rebellion in Gultepa Square in the second part of the city of Andijan, from a separate Ural Cossack face, Kuntayev

was injured by touching a stone on his head, three people died from the rebels, 8 were wounded. 22 people were detained from the heads of the uprising, transferred to the investigative body. On July 10, in the village of Dalvarzin, owned by the Oltinkul Department, the insurgents killed the head of the Department, Mulla Khakimbek Mulla Rozibekov and his companions. 32 people from the Chiefs of the uprising were detained and transferred to prison [3.98-99].

On July 11, in a raised uprising in the village of Chuvama in the Maygir Department, chuvama ellikbashi Kipchoqboy Boymirzayev was killed. Of the leaders of the uprising, 16 people were arrested and given to the investigation. On July 12, in the village of Kholmurod-Kakhancha in the section of the Fisherman, the village elder Eson Ali Rahimkulov was killed and 2 people from the organizers of the uprising were imprisoned. A similar uprising took place in the village of Bekabad in the Yorbashi section, Sufikishlak on the Sultanabad front, and in the village of Luja in the Norin section. Uprisings also took place in the villages of Kapa, Hindimozor, Yatma, Elaton, Mirobod, Khodjabod (in the fishing department), Forestbek, Andijan district. Talaygina part of the participants in the uprising were arrested.

At the same time as Margilan, an uprising was also raised in the city of Namangan. On July 11, 1,500 people gathered in the Wrestling area of the Labbaytaga genius in Namangan. The judge of the genius of labbaytaga immediately delivered a message to the pristav about the popular uprising. Pristav V.Dombrovsky arrived with a military unit armed to the Tooth-Nail. A crowd of men, women and children V.He demanded that dombrovsky stop drawing up a list mobilizing for Labor. Having learned about the expansion of the uprising, captain Rumyansev arrived with his rota. This ardent nationalist captain ordered the population to be shot from dab-durust. Pristav Dombrovsky admits that the rebels were unarmed and, despite the great looting, took hard with the military and police. They attacked the police and wanted to pull the pistol of pristav Fedorov, even the rebel Jamaliddin Uvaysov pulled the sword of one policeman.

Of the participants in the Namangan uprising, 84 people were sentenced to prison terms for various periods.

In clashes at 17 places in the Fergana Valley, the local population in particular from both sides made a lot of victims; 5 people were killed and 109 wounded. Of the wounded, 28 others later died. But the deliberately reduced indication of these numbers was later recognized by the colonial authorities

themselves. In particular, the military governor of the Fergana region wrote that it is difficult to know how many casualties were actually inflicted by sabali, who died in riots and took most of the wounded from the battlefield at a quick opportunity by the population.

On July 11, a wave of folk movements rose in the Old City part of Tashkent. The crowd gathered: "we will die if we die but we will not give our children!", "Let the tyrant king himself die!", "How long does he crush us?"shouted from all sides. To suppress the uprising, a punitive detachment led by Kolesnikov arrived. During the uprising, Colonel N. Ye. Kolesnikov tried to calm the crowd of several martoba. When one of the rebels was thrown at N. Ye.Kolesnikov with his sword in his hands, he shot this man from a pistol and killed him. After that, the blood of the haloyik boiled and sounded the voices "hit". In the crowd, a gymnasium student named Mahmud Mirsoatov said, " beat the Mirshabs!"called people to attack. From the rebels, Mirkosim Isamuhammedov disconnected the telephone cable with his partner. After the birth of the threat of the invasion of the crowd into the Office of the administration, they were shot at by order of N. Ye.Kolesnikov.

As a result, 11 people were killed and 15 wounded. Of the women, Rizvonbibi Ahmadkhanova was killed, Zadurbibi Musamuhammedova was wounded. Soon after the tragedy in the courtyard of the administration, the head of the city of Tashkent O.O.Kochin arrived. This is how he described the story he saw; "when I came to the police department, we came across a crowd of men and women on the street, around the administration and in part in the courtyard. The crowd consisted of several thousand people, among whom lay dead and wounded. On the street going to the police department, some people tried to complain about someone, explaining to me something very confusing. All the men and wives here seem humiliated and oppressed. When I entered the police department, I saw that all the Old City mirshabs were holding pistols in their hands. In front of the office building, the phone lies with the cable disconnected. Inside the office, I saw fragments of brick and stone, broken doors and windows. Military units had not yet arrived. Without taking into account the proposal to ask for the spread of the crowd, the noise was heard. Soon after, they began to take the dead and wounded and provide medical assistance. Until that moment, the division of the military educational institution and the mirshabs of the new city of Tashkent came to the administration. After that, the military units also arrived, surrounded the crowd from the side of the street and managed to disperse them.

As long as a group of Rebels went to Beshyagoch to attack the apartment of mirshab Mirkomil"[4.89-90]

The Tsarist government arrested and tried many people after suppressing the uprising. Of the active participants in the uprising, etikloz Abdurahman Qayumsofiyev and the black worker Mirkosim Shomammedov were sentenced to death by hanging. Of the workers, Tajiboy Yunuskhajayev, Ghulam Kamolov, Yulchi Ibrahimov, Nizamiddin Khoja Zainiddin Khojev, poor peasant Murodkhoja Mahmudali Hojev, Jacob Murodjabayev and others were sentenced to long-term exile or imprisonment.

Instead of 200,470 people to be sent, the Tsarist administration was able to mobilize practically more than 123,000 laborers. Of these, 101,600 tachsisi were sent to the western part of Russia, 4,000 to Siberia, 7,405 to the Caucasus. More than 10,000 people were used in the Turkestan territory itself. Laborers used betinim under strict control in military and industrial enterprises, mines, railway construction, forests and farms of some capitalists. They suffered a lot from hunger, humiliation, hard work. Many died from frostbite, various diseases, or were disabled for a lifetime.

References:

1. Tursunov H. The popular uprising of 1916 in Uzbekistan. – T.: Uzbekistan, 1966. - 170 pages
2. Ismailova J. National liberation struggles in the Fergana Valley. - T.: Ghafur Ghulam Publishing House. 2003 - 320 pages
3. Kovalev AP The rear workers of Turkestan during the First World War. Tashkent. 1957 The same: the revolutionary situation of 1915-1917 and its manifestation in Turkestan. Tashkent. 1971
4. Kastelskaya Z.D. The main prerequisites for the 1916 uprising in Uzbekistan M., 1972
5. Sodikov H. Turkestan's colonial policy and the struggle for independence (20th century) - Tashkent.1994
6. Akhmadzhanov G.A. Russian Empire in Central Asia (history and historiography of the colonial policy of tsarism in Turkestan). - T.: 1995
7. Suyunova A. The national liberation struggle of 1916 in Turkestan (on the example of Syrdarya region). - T.: 1997. - 131 pages
8. Zivoveva D. National Liberation Movement in Turkestan. - T.:Ghafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art,2000. - 176 pages